

The Effect of Nickel on the Impact Properties of the

$\text{Co,Cr-Cr}_{7-x}\text{Co}_x\text{C}_3$ Eutectic Composite

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Abstract

The impact strength of eutectic $\text{Co,Cr,Ni-Cr}_{7-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{C}_3$ (10 wt.% Ni) composites was measured as a function of temperature utilizing notched DVMK standard samples. The results were compared with similar measurements on the eutectic composite base material $\text{Co,Cr-Cr}_{7-x}\text{Co}_x\text{C}_3$. Values greater than 0.5 kpm/cm^2 were found, these being larger by a factor of 2 as compared with the unalloyed eutectic base material.

1. Introduction

Previous work on the impact strength of $\text{Co,Cr-Cr}_{6.1}\text{Co}_{0.9}\text{C}_3$ eutectic (Thompson 1971, Sahn and Varga 1972) showed that

- o the direction of highest impact strength was perpendicular to the Cr_7C_3 -fiber direction and that

o an impact strength minimum appeared in the temperature range between approximately 200 and 900°C,

the absolute level of impact strength being rather low (less than 0.5 kpm/cm²). Therefore, efforts were made to improve the absolute impact strength level and to even out the minimum in the medium temperature range.

An obvious way to improve impact behaviour appears to be by ductilization. Since Ni is known to ductilize a Co-matrix and also lower the hcp-fcc transition of Co-matrices (another desirable feature for improvement of the overall mechanical properties of Co-base alloys), it was chosen as alloying element in a "first order approach".

2. Experimental

The addition of 10% nickel to the basic Co-30 wt.% Cr-Cr_{6.1}Co_{0.9}C₃ eutectic alloy was found to lower the transformation temperature from 910°C to approximately 700°C without greatly affecting the other mechanical properties (Perry et al., 1973). An alloy of composition 40.5 Cr 9.7 Ni 2.18 C rest Co (wt. %) was directionally solidified in rod form (∅ 10 mm, 150 mm long) using a precision casting technique and a solidification speed of 6 cm/hr and a G/v between 10 and 30 K/cm² hr (Staub et al., 1972).

Metallography of the top and bottom rod ends of all samples indicated some structural variation.

DVMK specimens (figure 1) were machined from those rods exhibiting the best structure, three samples being made from each rod.

A typical structure is shown in figure 2. Impact measurements were made using a Zwick-impact machine with a 150 kpcm hammer. Direct resistance heating was used to heat the specimens to the test temperature. Temperatures were measured using a thermocouple (to 800°C) and a pyrometer (to 1150°C). Tests were carried out at room temperature, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, and 1150°C, two samples being tested at each temperature. The samples were only tested in the direction of highest impact strength, i.e. at right angles to the solidification direction (Thompson, 1971).

Evaluation of the results was supported by microscopy and scanning electron microscope analysis. The microprobe analyser was used to determine the nickel content in the carbide and the matrix (table 1 - constant carbon content was assumed).

3. Results

3.1 Impact Strength Measurements

The results are given in figure 3 along with previous results by Thompson (1971) as well as by Sahm and Varga (1972). The transformation temperatures have also been indicated. Two phenomena may be stated at once:

- o impact strength has increased by a factor of approximately 2;
- o the medium temperature range minimum appears to have been levelled out

when compared to the basic Co-Cr₇C₃ material.

3.2 The Effect of Ni-Additions on the Impact Behaviour of Co-Cr₇C₃ Eutectic

The fracture energy of in-situ composite materials may be said to be affected by (Kurz and Sahn, 1975):

- o crack initiation resistance,
- o crack propagation, i.e. plastic deformability of the phases involved,
- o interface energy effects (for example, decohesion at the phase interfaces or crack deviation along the interface).

Fracture under impact conditions (high rate deformation) probably initiates at a surface flaw. To a certain extent the modulus of elasticity may also play a role. The E-modulus of a composite may be estimated by both the rule of mixtures (signifying the volume fraction of the reinforcing phase) and the Hall-Petch relation (describing the effect of fiber spacing). Both phenomena, however, have not been changed much with respect to the corresponding ternary Co-Cr-C base alloy.

Therefore, this part of contributing fracture energy term will not be discussed further.

Crack propagation resistance in composites is promoted by higher ductility of matrix and/or fibers. It is well known (see, for example, Sims 1969) that Ni-additions to Co- or Co,Cr-alloys (according to table 1 there is 24 at.% Ni in the matrix) raise the ductility. This can probably be accounted for by the rise in stacking fault energy and thus easier plastic deformation along the numerous slip planes of a relatively undisturbed fcc-lattice. The fact that multiple fracture of fibres can be found in the Ni-alloyed material, table 2 and figure 5, phenomena not observed at temperatures below 900°C with the basic Co-Cr-C material (Sahm and Varga, 1972), also point in this direction.

The rising tendency of fracture energy above approximately 800°C may, in parts, be due to multiple cracking of the fibers. Extended multiple cracking of fibers commences between 600 and 850°C, figure 4 and table 2. At lower temperatures a practically pure single fracture behavior is observed. Experimental evidence gives no indication, however, as to an improved ductility of the fibres, as was observed in the base alloy with no Ni-additions (Sahm and Varga 1972). The fibers of the present material contain a small amount of Ni, table 1 (which corresponds to that found by Sahm and Lorenz 1972 and probably affects certain properties, e.g. ductile-to-brittle transition temperature).

The third point referred to above, interface effects, only contributes indirectly to impact strength in that an extremely good interface bond between matrix and fiber may be taken into consideration (Sahm and Varga 1972). High interface bond strength supports single fracture mode. In accordance with these assumptions no decohesion of matrix and carbide fibers has been observed under impact conditions (slow deformation conditions do show longitudinal splitting of fibers, Sahm 1974, Scarlin 1974).

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Table 1: Ni-contents in matrix and carbide of directionally solidified monovariant eutectic alloy of the type Co, Ni, Cr - $\text{Cr}_{7-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{C}_3$ (Hildebrandt and Demny 1974)

total Ni-content	carbide fractions in terms of the formula: $\text{Cr}_{7-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{C}_3$				matrix, at. %		
	Cr	Co	Ni	C	Co	Cr	Ni
5	5,94	1	0,06	3	61	32	7
10 ⁺	6,0	0,85	0,15	3	57	29	14
15	6,1	0,75	0,15	3	48	32	20
20	6,1	0,75	0,15	3	44	32	24

⁺Only this alloy was used for these investigations

Table 2: Fiber fractures observed near fracture surface

T °C	fracture mode	average distance of fiber fractures from ruptured surface
20 200	single	20 - 30 μm
		40 - 50 μm
400		50 - 100 μm
600		80 - 130 μm
800 1000 1150	multiple	60 - 100 μm
		120 - 170 μm
		100 - 400 μm

Figure 1: DVMK Specimen

27 μm

Figure 2: Photograph showing the general structure of the $\text{Co, Cr, Ni-Cr}_{7-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Ni}_y\text{C}_3$ (10 wt.% Ni) material

Figure 3: Impact strength variation with temperature

Figure 4: Distance variation (l) of cracked carbide from the fracture surface

a) 400°C

11 μm

b) 1150°C

11 μm

Figure 5: Photographs showing the crack variation at
a) 400°C and b) 1150°C